

reactivity of Co(III) and mixture of nitro and nitrito in the complexes.

Thus the trends in magnetic susceptibility and chemical shift values show increasing ligand field strength as one moves down the series of complexes in Table I. This is observed directly in the relative values of E_{dd} for complexes accordingly⁷.

It is also interesting to note that the observed and calculated values in σ and χ_p are some what deviating. This may be due to some factors such as covalent bonding of ligands with Co(III), uncertainties in the values of diamagnetic susceptibilities used for evaluating terms, configurational interaction (cis and trans), the distortion in the octahedral structure of complexes of Co(III), etc. which were not considered in the theory^{9,10,11}.

The data σ , χ_p and E_{dd} also may be utilised very clearly to establish ligand field strength of ligands such as ONO^- , H_2O , NO_2 and NH_3 , to study nitrito and nitro isomers and to distinguish cis and trans isomers in these nitro-ammine Co(III) complexes (Table I.)

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Extraction of Manganese(II) with Salicylaldoxime—Synergic Effect of Pyridine*

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OXIMES (mono and di) of carbonyl compounds are extensively employed as extraction photometric reagents for many metal ions¹. A survey of literature has shown that very little work on oximes for extraction photometric determination of manganese(II) is reported. Flagg and Furman² reported that salicylaldoxime reacts with many metal ions including manganese. However no work was reported on the extraction photometry of manganese with this oxime. Gorbach *et al.*³ made casual mention about the possible extraction of manganese with salicylaldoxime with chloroform. The present authors observed that the oximate complex of manganese(II) formed in alkaline solutions is quantitatively extractable into *n*-butanol. However the yellowish brown colour of the butanolic layer was unstable and deepened with time, even though the determination of the metal ion⁴ was possible, if the measurements are completed within 30 minutes. It is found from the literature* that this phenomenon of colour change is a common occurrence due to aerial oxidation of Mn(II) and addition of pyridine was suggested to overcome this difficulty. Present authors however noticed that the colour of *n*-butanolic layer was unstable even after the addition of pyridine. In contrast to the behaviour in *n*-butanol, the metal is extracted completely into toluene in presence of pyridine. The colour was also stable for long times. There is negligible extraction into toluene in the absence of pyridine. The organic layer is colourless, if the extraction is carried out without salicylaldoxime. Extraction photometric study of Mn(II) with salicylaldoxime into toluene in presence of pyridine is therefore carried out and the results are communicated herewith.

The studies pertaining to the effect of pH on the reaction between Mn(II) and the oxime revealed that there is yellow colour formation in the range 8-10. The soluble coloured complex was extracted into toluene in presence of pyridine. The absorbance of the organic phase obtained at pH 10 measured against the solvent blank showed highest value at 420 nm in the visible range (400-700 nm). The absorbance is constant for several weeks. The aqueous phase after extraction showed zero absorbance. Chemical examination of the aqueous phase showed that a quantitative recovery is achieved when the concentration of the oxime is atleast 20 fold excess and pyridine is 5% in the organic phase.

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Recommended Procedure

5 ml of ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer (pH adjusted to 10), 1 ml of sodium perchlorate (1 M), 1 ml of the oxime solution ($10^{-1}M$), 0.5 ml pyridine and different aliquots of $MnSO_4$ solution ($10^{-3}M$) are taken in a 25 ml separatory funnel. The volume of the aqueous phase is maintained at 10 ml by adding requisite volume of distilled water, 10 ml of toluene is added to the contents of the funnel and shaken well, for five minutes. After equilibration, the organic layer is separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance measured against solvent blank at 420 nm. The organic phase obtained in the extraction carried out without the metal ion is used as the solvent blank. The good linear plot obtained between the amount of the metal ion and the absorbance showed that manganese can be estimated by the present method accurately in the range 0-6 $\mu g/ml$. The molar absorptivity (ϵ) and the Sandell sensitivity (S) at 420 nm are 0.58×10^4 lit. mole $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ and 0.0095 $\mu g/cm^2$ respectively. The standard deviation is 0.005. Zn(II) and Ni(II) do not interfere. More than 2 fold excess of Fe(III) interferes in the determination.

The Coleman⁶ graphical analysis of the organic layer showed that only a single species is responsible for the colour of the organic phase. Absorbance of the toluene layer increased with increase of pyridine upto 5% and later remains constant.

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Thermal Studies of Absorption Behaviour of Some Organic Compounds on Partially Co(II) and Ni(II)-Exchanged AW500 Zeolites

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PARTIALLY cation-exchanged samples of synthetic zeolite AW500 were prepared with cobalt(II) chloride-hexahydrate and nickel(II) chloride-hexahydrate. Thermal behaviours of these zeolites after interaction with pyridine, triethanol amine, trichloroethylene and 1, 1, 2, 2-tetrachloroethane have been investigated by thermogravimetry, differential thermal analysis and differential thermogravimetry. Experimental details and the thermal behaviours of these exchanged samples along with data on absorbed samples of partially-exchanged Cu(II) and Hg(II)-AW500 with these organic compounds have been communicated earlier¹⁻³. The thermal data obtained with the absorbed samples of Ni(II)- and Co(II)-AW500 zeolites have been tabulated (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Complex formation reactions of pyridine and its derivatives with both cobalt(II) and nickel(II) compounds have been studied by several workers⁴⁻⁷. Cobalt(II) was found to give a chelate with triethanolamine where the ligand was tetradentate giving a trigonal bipyramidal configuration around the metal atom⁸. Nickel(II) on the other hand formed a polycondensed complex with the ligand⁹.

Infrared spectroscopic studies of pyridine adsorption on a series of oxide surfaces, mainly chemically modified SiO_2 , showed that two types of Lewis acid centres were formed differing in the coordination of the exposed central atoms at the surface. Among the bonds formed during adsorption, the coordinate bond of pyridine on electron acceptor centres of surface mixed oxides of SiO_2 was the strongest¹⁰. The same authors¹¹ reported the appearance of a broad, relatively weak band at ~ 2700 cm $^{-1}$ due to pyridine adsorption on various siliceous surfaces. The band was assigned to the $N^+—H$ stretching vibration of pyridinium ions.

In the present study involving pyridine adsorption no clear indication of the nature of interaction is available as neither the temperature of water elimination nor the pattern of thermal decomposition reliably indicates structure or bonding¹². Adsorption of triethanolamine on the zeolites to a considerable extent is however indicated by the presence of an unusually strong exothermic peak in the